

Teachers' Compliance and Commitment to the Implementation of Child Protection Policy

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Abstract:

Department Order No. 40, series of 2012, also known as the DepEd Child Protection Policy pursuant to Article 15, Section 3(2) of the 1987 Constitution, that the state shall defend the right of children to assistance, including proper care and nutrition, and special protection from all forms of neglect, abuse, cruelty, exploitation, and other conditions prejudicial to their development (D. O. 40, series of 2012). Along this line, this study aimed to determine the extent of compliance and the level of commitment of teachers in the implementation of the Child Protection Policy (CPP) in one of the districts of a medium-sized school division in Central Philippines during the School Year 2022-2023. The study used 170 public elementary school teachers using a self-made survey questionnaire that has passed the rigorous tests of validity and reliability. Data gathered showed a great extent of compliance of teachers in the implementation of CPP in the areas of service delivery and community participation. Conversely, the level of teachers' commitment was found to be high. There was no significant difference in the extent of compliance and the level of commitment of teachers in the implementation of CPP when grouped according to the variables above. Lastly, there is a significant relationship between the extent of compliance and the level of commitment of teachers in implementing CPP. The study results call for various educators to further strengthen the implementation of the Child Protection Policy.

Keywords: Teacher's Compliance, commitment, child's protection policy, Organization Sustainability, service delivery, community participation.

Introduction:

Nature of Problem

Department Order No. 40, series of 2012, also known as the DepEd Child Protection Policy pursuant to Article 15, Section 3 of the 1987 Constitution, that the state shall defend the right of children to assistance, including proper care and nutrition, and special protection from all forms of neglect, abuse, cruelty, exploitation, and other conditions prejudicial to their development (D. O. 40, series of 2012).

The Facts for Life by UNICEF (2015) stated, "the right of the children to be safe and secure of their needs necessitate for their complete development and success in life." This is the importance of having a child protection policy and program in schools and communities. Child Protection Policy (CPP) provides special protection to children who are gravely threatened or endangered by circumstances that affect their normal development and over which they have no control. It also assists the concerned agencies in their rehabilitation.

However, despite these initiatives and interventions, the Department of Education Central Office has received more than 1,700 reports of child abuse and bullying in schools, and out of these cases, only 60% have been resolved (Dep. Ed, 2019). In the district where this study is conducted, a total of 38 cases relative to child abuse and bullying have been reported for the past three (3) years. These were committed by family members, relatives, school personnel, and classmates, while complaints of all types of bullying reached more than 130 cases (DSWD Bacolod, 2019).

A child's academic performance may be negatively impacted by any impending threats; therefore, as a public elementary school teacher, the school's senior advocate of the Child Protection Policy (CPP), and the researcher who has been exposed to handling child abuse and neglect cases for the past five years and had been interviewing victimized children and parents who were mostly alleged as assailants. In the same school, not too long ago, a male teacher was once dismissed for child abuse. Privy to these school scenarios, the researcher was motivated to conduct this study.

Current State of Knowledge

Child abuse is a widespread issue. It happens in every nation and every society. It involves the maltreatment of children and teenagers on a physical, sexual, emotional, and neglectful basis. Delegates, support staff, and other conference-related personnel are just a few of the individuals who may expose children and adolescents to various forms of exploitation, abuse, violence, and neglect in homes, communities, institutions, organizations, and private and public spaces. This Child Protection Policy was created to address and safeguard children and adolescents from possible abuse and exploitation. In the Philippines, national policy and program responses to child abuse are provided by a variety of government bodies and institutions. The aforementioned entities comprise the Department of Social Welfare and Development (DSWD), the Barangay Community Councils, the Council for the Welfare of Children (CWC), and the Committee for the Special Protection of Children (CSPC) situated within the Department of Justice. The government's main agency for welfare is the DSWD. Its responsibilities include setting standards, granting accreditation, offering advisory services to individuals, groups, and public and private institutions involved in social welfare initiatives, keeping an eye on these entities' performance, and enforcing adherence to standards. The DSWD offers and oversees various family-centered welfare programs, domestic and international adoption, and residential care. The primary government organization for children's concerns and policy in the Philippines is the Council for the Welfare of Children, a different organization entrusted with creating, organizing, and overseeing children's policies and keeping an eye on the country's children's rights (UNICEF, 2015).

The Child-Safe Organizations training course and toolkit provide a framework for creating and effectively implementing child protection policies within regional organizations that serve and work with children. The training is primarily intended for community-based and local organizations needing access to an internal child safety specialist or policy department. Children's best interests are the most crucial consideration for organizations when creating policies and guidelines. A wide range of ideas, rules, regulations, procedures, and practices are called "child protection" to shield children from purposeful and accidental harm. The protection of children in international schools is covered under the phrase "child protection" in this paper (AISA, 2014). Self-harm is included in this term as well. A child protection policy is a declaration of intent that shows a commitment to safeguarding students from external and internal harm. It lays out exactly what is needed to ensure their safety. It helps to establish a secure and encouraging atmosphere for kids and shows that the school is taking its responsibilities seriously. This means schools will offer suitable child safety lessons backed by an explicit curriculum to improve children's comprehension of abuse prevention. Concerns about child protection encompass anything from suspected, reported, self-reported, or seen child abuse by anyone connected to the school, all of which need to be looked into and dealt with appropriately. "Any forms of physical and/or emotional ill-treatment, sexual abuse, neglect or negligent treatment or commercial or other exploitation, resulting in actual or potential harm to the child's health, survival, development or dignity in the context of a relationship of responsibility, trust or power" is what the World Health Organization defines as child abuse (WHO, 2015).

Theoretical Underpinnings

This study was anchored on the following theories: The Theory of Compliance by Gary Becker and George Stigler (1974), and the Theory of Commitment by John Meyer and Natalie Allen (1991). These theories will serve as the basis and framework for the conduct of this study.

The Compliance Theory. Becker and Stigler (1974) initially based the premise of their work "*that lone actors can choose among the various alternatives presented to them based on greater gain and least cost*" (Etienne, 2014). As such, the recipients of public action are egotistical, utilitarian, and willing to decide their strategy once and for all in reference to a fixed standard. The theory also takes into account the fact that individual choices are inserted in pre-existing structures of relations. In other words, a decision theory approach, like the one used by Becker, assumes that recipients make choices as a function of a fixed set of constraints, as it considers (mainly endogenous) variations in these constraints. This theory matches the need of the study to establish the extent of teachers' compliance in implementing CPP in schools throughout the country. Its importance is demonstrated by how teachers implement the program because of the legal mandate to do so; they suffer penalties for non-compliance.

Next, the Theory of Commitment supports the needed framework of this study. Meyer and Allen (1991) explained that commitment is a psychological state and that it has three distinct components that affect how a person feels about the organization that he works for. Affection for the job, the fear of loss, and the sense of obligation to stay are the three major components of this theory. The Theory of Commitment relates to this study because it explains that teachers' adherence to the implementation of CPP is part of the position or job they are currently holding. Teachers' commitment allows them to identify with the organization's goals and values to protect children and uphold their rights as human beings.

Objectives of the Study

This study aimed to determine the extent of compliance, level of commitment, and level of difficulties of teachers in the implementation of the Child Protection Policy (CPP) in a District of a medium-sized school division in Central

Philippines during the School Year 2022-2023. Specifically, this study sought to provide answers to the following questions: 1) the extent of compliance of the teachers in the implementation of CPP according to the areas of service delivery and community participation; 2) the level of commitment of the teachers in the implementation of CPP according to the aforementioned areas; 3) the extent of compliance of the teachers in the implementation of CPP when grouped according to the aforementioned variables; 4) the level of commitment of teachers in the implementation of CPP when grouped according to the aforementioned variables; 5) the significant difference in the extent of compliance of teachers in the implementation of CPP when grouped and compared according to the aforementioned variables; 6) the significant difference in the level of commitment of teachers in the implementation of CPP when grouped and compared according to the aforementioned variables; and 7) the significant relationship between extent of compliance and level of commitment of teachers in the implementation of CPP.

Research Methodology:

This section describes the methodology that was followed in carrying out the study. This includes research design, locale of the study, respondents of the study, data gathering instrument and its reliability and validity, data gathering procedure, analytical schemes, and statistical tools.

Research Design

This study used the descriptive research design to determine the teachers' extent of compliance and the level of commitment to the implementation of the Child Protection Program (CPP) in a medium-sized Division in the Central Philippines for the School Year 2022-2023. According to Calmorin (2016), a descriptive research design method focuses on the present situation and aims to find the new truth. The truth may have different forms, such as an increased quantity of knowledge, a further generalization, or a new "law," an improved insight into a factor.

Respondents

The study's respondents were 170 teachers from a total population of 301. Since the number of respondents is quite large, stratified sampling and random sampling techniques were used, using the Cochran formula to find the sample size. To get the percentage, the respondents from each district/school are divided by the total number of respondents and multiplied by the sample size. The researcher randomly selected the respondents from each school using the lottery technique.

Instruments

This paper used a self-made survey questionnaire to gather data. It was subjected to validity (4.84-excellent) and reliability (0.719-Acceptable for compliance and 0.770-Acceptable for commitment). All of them were interpreted as worthy and good, respectively. This consists of two parts: Part I gathered the information needed to profile the respondents, and this included details like age, sex, highest educational attainment, and length of service, while Part II contained topics to determine the compliance and commitment of teachers in the implementation of the Children Protection Program (CPP). These areas across the said categories included service delivery and community participation composed of five (5) line items or a total of 15 items per area, and where respondents will be asked to rate each item using the 5-point Likert Scale as 5 (always), 4 (often), 3 (sometimes), 2 (rarely) and 1 (almost never).

Data-Gathering Procedure

After the instrument was found to be valid and reliable, the researcher sent a letter to the school division Superintendent (SDS) requesting approval to conduct the study, stating its objectives and assuring the confidentiality of the information and responses of the teacher-respondents. When permission was obtained, the researcher informed the district supervisor, the principal, and the teachers about the nature and procedures of the study. The researcher then reproduced and administered the questionnaire to the respondents. Thereafter, the assigned statistician gathered, checked, encoded, and interpreted questionnaires with the aid of the Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS).

Data Analysis and Statistical Treatment

Objective no. 1 used the descriptive analytical scheme and mean to determine the extent of compliance of the teachers in the implementation of CPP according to service delivery and community participation;

Objective no. 2 used the descriptive analytical scheme and mean to determine the level of commitment of the teachers in the implementation of CPP according to the aforementioned areas;

Objective no.3 used the descriptive analytical scheme and mean to determine the extent of compliance of the teachers in the implementation of CPP when grouped according to the aforementioned variables;

Objective no.4 used the descriptive analytical scheme and mean to determine the level of commitment of teachers in the implementation of CPP when grouped according to the aforementioned variables;

Objective No. 5 used comparative analytical scheme and Mann-Whitney U Test to determine the significant difference in the extent of compliance of teachers in the implementation of CPP when grouped and compared according to the aforementioned variables;

Objective No. 6 used comparative analytical scheme and Mann-Whitney U Test to determine the significant difference in the level of commitment of teachers in the implementation of CPP when grouped and compared according to the aforementioned variables; and

Objective No. 7 used relational analytical scheme and Spearman rho to determine the the significant relationship between extent of compliance and level of commitment of teachers in the implementation of CPP.

Ethical Considerations

This research paper strives to minimize the risk of harm to its target respondents by assuring them of the confidentiality of their responses and protecting their anonymity throughout the entire research process. At the onset, this researcher secures their free, prior informed consent and assures them of their right to withdraw from their research participation if deemed necessary.

Results and Discussions

This section comprises the gathered data based on the researcher's study objectives. The analysis and interpretation of data were presented in tabular form, along with the study results' implications.

Table 1
Extent of Compliance of Teachers in CPP Implementation in Service Delivery

Area	Mean	Interpretation
B. Service Delivery		
<i>As a teacher, I am ...</i>		
1. educating learners to approach me or any teacher to report any instance of bullying in school or any form of abuse they encounter.	3.44	Moderate Extent
2. working closely with our team in gathering information if there are reported cases of violence against children.	4.12	Great Extent
3. providing suggestions on how to provide quicker solutions to complaints.	4.08	Great Extent
4. helping in the identification and protection of the victim.	3.34	Moderate Extent
5. cooperating with the school's initiatives in providing faster resolution to reported cases.	4.08	Great Extent
Overall Mean	3.81	Great Extent

Table 1 shows the overall mean score of 3.81, which is interpreted to a great extent. Item no. 2 got the highest mean of 4.12, interpreted as a great extent, and item no. 4 got the lowest mean of 3.34, interpreted as a moderate extent. To be able to protect the victim, they must first be identified. This process is paramount and must be carried out regardless of the circumstances. The teachers are obliged to extend the help the victim may need. This was corroborated by Sinanan (2017), who claimed that school staff, especially teachers and school psychologists, are the first line of defense in preventing child abuse. Teachers are crucial in identifying and reporting cases of child abuse. The bonds they build with their students can aid in the detection of child maltreatment. They are in a unique position to see the warning symptoms of child abuse because of their work, which requires them to have constant contact with children.

Table 2
Extent of Compliance of Teachers in CPP Implementation in Community Participation

Area	Mean	Interpretation
C. Community Participation		
<i>As a teacher, I am ...</i>		
1. keeping in touch with our community leaders to assist victims and help their families cope with violent experiences.	3.49	Great Extent
2. providing support, financially or morally, to the children of our community who are victims of violence at home.	4.00	Great Extent

3. giving assistance to the parents of the victims by guiding them to seek counseling or professional help.	3.85	Great Extent
4. helping the community by training the parents on what to do when they or their children are subjected to violent situations.	3.49	Moderate Extent
5. assisting community leaders or social workers ensure that victims are fully protected and the incident is properly reported to authorities.	3.59	Great Extent
Overall Mean	3.68	Great Extent

Table 2 shows the overall mean score of 3.68, which is interpreted to a great extent. Item no. 2 got the highest mean of 4.00, which was interpreted to a great extent. Meanwhile, item no. 4 got the lowest mean of 3.49, interpreted as a moderate extent. The community's support is very important in the prevention and implementation of the Child Protection Policy. Teachers who work with the community to stop crimes committed against young children are extremely valuable as well. However, as the result of the study revealed, some teachers may need more time to get engaged with community affairs. One of the top priorities in crime prevention needs to be the prevention of violence against children. A comprehensive approach to end violence against children should include preventive measures, which draw on our growing understanding of the factors that lead to violence against children and address the dangers of violence to which children are exposed (United Nations, 2014, Article 12).

Table 3
Level of Commitment of Teachers in CPP Implementation in Service Delivery

Area	Mean	Interpretation
B. Service Delivery		
<i>As a teacher, I am ...</i>		
1. educating learners to approach me or any teacher to report any instance of bullying in school or any form of abuse they encounter.	3.81	High Level
2. working closely with our team in gathering information if there are reported cases of violence against children.	4.05	High Level
3. providing suggestions on how to provide quicker solutions to complaints.	3.92	High Level
4. helping in the identification and protection of the victim.	3.76	High Level
5. cooperating with the initiatives of the school in providing faster resolution to reported cases.	3.55	High Level
Overall Mean	3.82	High Level

Table 3 shows the overall mean score of 3.82, which is interpreted as a high level. Item no. 2 got the highest mean of 4.05 and item no. 5 got the lowest mean of 3.55 both interpreted as a high level. In every school, all stakeholders need to give their share in implementing the CPP. Teachers are lead stakeholders in these trying times. It is in the best interest of every child if teachers are non-evasive and help in providing information to quickly resolve child abuse cases. This finding is consistent with Dardo's (2019) assertion that, during the previous 30 years, efforts to prevent child abuse have increased dramatically. A portion of this growth is due to the implementation of new governmental laws and the increase of formal services, including home visiting programs, support groups, parenting education workshops, and child safety instruction. It takes more than just improving parental behavior to prevent child abuse; rather, it takes fostering an environment that makes "doing better" simpler. It is nevertheless necessary to educate the public about the tremendous harm that child abuse and neglect can do to a kid's ability to develop normally.

Table 4
Level of Commitment of Teachers in CPP Implementation in terms of Community Participation

Area	Mean	Interpretation
C. Community Participation		
<i>As a teacher, I am ...</i>		
1. keeping in touch with our community leaders to assist victims and help their families cope with violent experiences.	3.62	High Level
2. providing support, financially or morally, to the children of our community who are victims of violence at home.	3.85	High Level
3. giving assistance to the parents of the victims by guiding them to seek counseling or professional help.	4.02	High Level
4. helping the community by training the parents on what to do when they or their children are subjected to violent situations.	3.57	High Level
5. assisting community leaders or social workers in making sure that victims are fully protected and the incident is properly reported to authorities.	4.12	High Level
Overall Mean	3.84	High Level

Table 4 shows the overall mean of 3.84 interpreted as high level. Item no. 5, got the highest mean of 4.12 and item no. 4, got the lowest mean score of 3.57, both interpreted as a high level. The collaboration of the community is important, while the cooperation of the teachers in the same community is a moving experience. Community response to child maltreatment could be much easier and faster if all stakeholders are cooperating with each other. The WHO (2016) reports that a considerable proportion of children worldwide suffer from maltreatment, which can have long-lasting effects on the victims. Reactions to child maltreatment, particularly in the Global South, are inadequately studied and understood. Despite the importance and influence of policies regarding child abuse, research on the subject is still in its infancy in the Philippines. Growing global awareness of the need for children to be raised in stable, safe surroundings free from abuse and neglect has increased the urgency of policy imperatives in this area.

Table 5
Extent of Compliance of Teachers in CPP Implementation in Service Delivery According to Age

Area	Younger		Older	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
B. Service Delivery				
<i>As a teacher, I am ...</i>				
1. Educating learners to approach me or any teacher to report any instance of bullying in school or any form of abuse they encounter.	3.46	Moderate Extent	3.40	Moderate Extent
2. working closely with our team in gathering information if there are reported cases of violence against children.	4.21	Great Extent	4.01	Great Extent
3. providing suggestions on how to provide quicker solutions to complaints.	4.04	Great Extent	4.14	Great Extent
4. helping in the identification and protection of the victim.	3.34	Moderate Extent	3.34	Moderate Extent
5. cooperating with the initiatives of the school in providing faster resolution to reported cases.	4.13	Great Extent	4.00	Great Extent
Overall Mean	3.84	Great Extent	3.78	Great Extent

Table 5 shows the overall mean scores of 3.84 for the younger group and 3.78 for the older group; both were interpreted to a great extent. Item no. 2 got the highest mean score of 4.21 for the younger group, and item no. 3 got the highest mean score of 4.14 for the older group, both were interpreted as great extent. Meanwhile, item no. 4 got the lowest mean score of 3.34 for the younger group and 3.34 for the older group; both were interpreted as moderate extent. Both younger and older respondents share the same issue that some teachers may have problems assisting CPP-designated school officials in identifying and extending protection to the victims. One of the reasons could be teachers' fear of being entangled in legal battles during the whole process. There are, of course, other reasons. It is important for schools to encourage teachers to provide voluntary assistance in identifying and helping victims. A child's safety from abuse and harm is the school's responsibility while they are enrolled. The school must establish a secure learning environment, recognize students in distress or danger, and take appropriate action. Employees at the school must also get child protection training (The Government of Northern Ireland, 2023).

Table 6
Extent of Compliance of Teachers in CPP Implementation in Community Participation According to Age

Area	Younger		Older	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
C. Community Participation				
<i>As a teacher, I am ...</i>				
1. keeping in touch with our community leaders to assist victims and help their families cope with violent experiences.	3.37	Moderate Extent	3.60	Great Extent
2. providing support, financially or morally, to the children of our community who are victims of violence at home.	3.96	Great Extent	4.05	Great Extent
3. giving assistance to the parents of the victims by guiding them to seek counseling or professional help.	3.82	Great Extent	3.88	Great Extent
4. helping the community by training the parents on what to do when they or their children are subjected to violent situations.	3.41	Moderate Extent	3.64	Great Extent
5. assisting community leaders or social workers in making sure that victims are fully protected and the	3.55	Great Extent	3.66	Great Extent

incident is properly reported to authorities.

Overall Mean	3.62	Great Extent	3.77	Great Extent
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Table 6 shows the overall mean scores of 3.62 for the younger group and 3.77 for the older group; both were interpreted to a great extent. Item no. 2 got the highest mean score of 3.96 for the younger group and 4.05 for the older group; both were interpreted to a great extent. Meanwhile, item no. 1 got the lowest mean score of 3.37 for the younger group, interpreted as moderate extent, and 3.60 for the older group, interpreted as great extent. This table underscores the fact that there are some teachers who are less engaged with the community effort to help victims of physical, sexual, or any form of abuse. While this is not compulsory, educators must realize that the community is rooting for them as learned individuals, and their collaboration with community leaders will significantly impact the CPP program implementation. Lloyd's (2018) study looked at the effects of domestic abuse on young children, children, and young adults' lives and education, as well as how the educational system might support these individuals. Teachers can be extremely helpful in assisting families in accessing welfare services since they are frequently the agency that has the longest and closest interaction with a kid who is a victim of domestic abuse. And teachers are crucial in spotting abuse indicators and providing referral routes, yet research shows they frequently lack confidence and knowledge for such work.

Table 7
Extent of Compliance of Teachers in CPP Implementation in Service Delivery According to Length of Service

Area	Shorter		Longer	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
B. Service Delivery				
<i>As a teacher, I am ...</i>				
1. educating learners to approach me or any teacher to report any instance of bullying in school or any form of abuse they encounter.	3.42	Moderate Extent	3.45	Moderate Extent
2. working closely with our team in gathering information if there are reported cases of violence against children.	4.20	Great Extent	4.03	Great Extent
3. providing suggestions on how to provide quicker solutions to complaints.	4.04	Great Extent	4.13	Great Extent
4. helping in the identification and protection of the victim.	3.31	Moderate Extent	3.38	Moderate Extent
5. cooperating with the initiatives of the school in providing faster resolution to reported cases.	4.14	Great Extent	4.00	Great Extent
Overall Mean	3.82	Great Extent	3.80	Great Extent

Table 7 shows the overall mean scores of 3.82 for the shorter group and 3.80 for the longer group; both were interpreted to a great extent. Item no. 2 got the highest mean score of 4.20 for the shorter group and item no. 3 with the highest mean score of 4.13 for the longer group; both were interpreted to a great extent. Meanwhile, item no. 4 got the lowest mean score of 3.31 for the shorter group and 3.38 for the longer group; both were interpreted as moderate extent. Regardless of tenure, the respondents indicated that their common issue is in helping to identify and protect child abuse victims. A small percentage of teachers are having issues helping the mentioned process, which could be attributed to low awareness or less desire to get involved for whatever reasons they may have. The schools have the obligation to ensure that teachers are up to their duty of defending children who are abused by their abusers. The function of teachers in responding to and preventing since child abuse and neglect are serious issues, each case must be handled individually and swiftly. Instructors must pinpoint the causes of their concerns, detect instances of child abuse and neglect, offer assistance both prior to and during the reporting of such incidents and ultimately work to avoid such incidents (Tower, 2017).

Table 8. *Extent of Compliance of Teachers in CPP Implementation in terms of Community Participation and Length of Service*

Area	Shorter		Longer	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
C. Community Participation				
<i>As a teacher, I am ...</i>				
1. keeping in touch with our community leaders to assist victims and help their families cope with violent experiences.	3.41	Moderate Extent	3.60	Great Extent
2. Provide support, financially or morally, to the children of our community who are victims of violence at home.	3.99	Great Extent	4.01	Great Extent
3. giving assistance to the parents of the victims by guiding them to seek counseling or professional help.	3.85	Great Extent	3.84	Great Extent

4. helping the community by training the parents on what to do when they or their children are subjected to violent situations.	3.40	Moderate Extent	3.60	Great Extent
5. assisting community leaders or social workers in making sure that victims are fully protected, and the incident is properly reported to authorities.	3.57	Great Extent	3.62	Great Extent
Overall Mean	3.64	Great Extent	3.74	Great Extent

Table 8 shows the overall mean scores of 3.64 for the shorter group and 3.74 for the longer group; both were interpreted to a great extent. Item no. 2 got the highest mean score of 3.99 for the shorter group and 4.01 for the longer group; both were interpreted to a great extent. Meanwhile, Item no. 4 got the lowest mean score of 3.40 for shorter group, interpreted as moderate extent and items no. 1 and 4 got the lowest mean score 3.60 for longer group, interpreted as great extent. This implies that there is a need for some teachers to be deeply involved with the community effort to minimize, if not fully stop, the instances of child abuse in any form or nature. As educational leaders, teachers are looked up to in the community; thus, their engagement in the effort to make CPP work would be important. Dealing with maltreated children has numerous challenges. Maintaining some normalcy with the child is the hardest part. In addition to keeping students safe, educators are responsible for educating students so that they will one day be able to leave the harmful environment. Furthermore, instructors frequently hesitate to speak with an abusive parent about a problem at school out of concern that the child may experience abuse at home once more (DeWitt, 2021).

Table 9

Extent of Compliance of Teachers in CPP Implementation in terms of Service Delivery and Family Income

Area	Lower		Higher	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
B. Service Delivery <i>As a teacher, I am ...</i>				
1. educating learners to approach me or any teacher to report any instance of bullying in school or any form of abuse they encounter.	3.53	Great Extent	3.31	Moderate Extent
2. working closely with our team in gathering information if there are reported cases of violence against children.	4.18	Great Extent	4.04	Great Extent
3. providing suggestions on how to provide quicker solutions to complaints.	4.03	Great Extent	4.15	Great Extent
4. helping in the identification and protection of the victim.	3.43	Moderate Extent	3.21	Moderate Extent
5. cooperating with the initiatives of the school in providing faster resolution to reported cases.	4.06	Great Extent	4.10	Great Extent
Overall Mean	3.85	Great Extent	3.76	Great Extent

Table 9 shows the overall mean scores of 3.85 for the lower group and 3.76 for the higher group; both were interpreted to a great extent. Item no. 2 got the highest mean score of 4.18 for the lower group and 4.04 for the higher group; both were interpreted to a great extent. Meanwhile, item no. 4 got the lowest mean score of 3.43 for the lower group and 3.21 for the higher group; both were interpreted as moderate extent. Both lower and higher-income respondents agree that some teachers have issues in extending the necessary help to the victims of this case. Many organizations refer to their work and programs in the community or larger social context as "child protection." This could cause misunderstandings when talking about the duties related to child protection and organizational management. We cannot overlook the more general child safety concerns that organizations deal with in the communities where they operate, such as police abuse, domestic violence, commercial sexual exploitation, etc. It is the duty of all organizations to take all reasonable precautions to safeguard the children with whom they come into touch, whether the harm is occurring within or outside the organization. However, the scope of this specific toolbox is limited to child safety within organizations, including hiring, managing, staff and kid behavior, and the physical environment of facilities (UNICEF, 2015).

Table 10

Extent of Compliance of Teachers in CPP Implementation in terms of Community Participation and Family Income

Area	Lower		Higher	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
C. Community Participation <i>As a teacher, I am ...</i>				
1. keeping in touch with our community leaders to assist victims and help their families cope with violent experiences.	3.48	Moderate Extent	3.53	Great Extent

2. Provide support, financially or morally, to the children of our community who are victims of violence at home.	3.97	Great Extent	4.04	Great Extent
3. giving assistance to the parents of the victims by guiding them to seek counseling or professional help.	3.84	Great Extent	3.86	Great Extent
4. helping the community by training the parents on what to do when they or their children are subjected to violent situations.	3.44	Moderate Extent	3.50	Great Extent
5. assisting community leaders or social workers in making sure that victims are fully protected and the incident is properly reported to authorities.	3.56	Great Extent	3.65	Great Extent
Overall Mean	3.66	Great Extent	3.72	Great Extent

Table 10 shows the overall mean scores of 3.66 for the lower group and 3.72 for the higher group; both were interpreted to a great extent. Item no. 2 got the highest mean score of 3.97 for the lower group and 4.04 for the higher group; both were interpreted to a great extent. Meanwhile, item no. 4 got the lowest mean score of 3.43 for the lower group, interpreted as moderate extent, and 3.50 for the higher group, interpreted as great extent. This reveals that there are teachers who are not fully engaged with the community, particularly in the effort to educate parents and their neighborhood regarding child abuse. This could be due to the fact that some teachers are not willing to be actively involved with the community. Child abuse is a widespread issue. It happens in every nation and in every society. It involves the maltreatment of children and teenagers on a physical, sexual, emotional, and neglectful basis. Almost invariably, it is avoidable. Delegates, support staff, and other conference-related personnel are just a few of the individuals who may expose children and adolescents to various forms of exploitation, abuse, violence, and neglect in homes, communities, institutions, organizations, and private and public spaces (Alombro, 2019).

Table 11
Level of Compliance of Teachers in CPP Implementation in terms of Service Delivery and Age Groupings

Area	Younger		Older	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
B. Service Delivery <i>As a teacher, I am ...</i>				
1. educating learners to approach me or any teacher to report any instance of bullying in school or any form of abuse they encounter.	3.82	High Level	3.78	High Level
2. working closely with our team in gathering information if there are reported cases of violence against children.	4.04	High Level	4.05	High Level
3. providing suggestions on how to provide quicker solutions to complaints.	3.97	High Level	3.85	High Level
4. helping in the identification and protection of the victim.	3.77	High Level	3.74	High Level
5. cooperating with the initiatives of the school in providing faster resolution to reported cases.	3.52	High Level	3.59	High Level
Overall Mean	3.82	High Level	3.80	High Level

Table 11 shows the overall mean scores of 3.82 for the younger group and 3.80 for the older group, which is interpreted as high. Item no. 2 got the highest mean score of 4.04 for the younger group and 4.05 for the older group, interpreted as a high level. Meanwhile, item no. 5 got the lowest mean score of 3.52 for the younger group and 3.59 for the older group, which can be interpreted as high. A wide range of ideas, rules, regulations, guidelines, and practices are referred to as "child protection" to shield children from purposeful and accidental harm. The protection of children in international schools is covered under the phrase "child protection" in this paper. Self-harm is included in this term as well. A child protection policy is a declaration of intent that shows a commitment to safeguarding students from external and internal harm and lays out exactly what is needed to ensure their safety. It shows that the school is taking its duty and obligation seriously and helps to establish a safe and positive atmosphere for the kids (AISA, 2016).

Table 12
Level of Compliance of Teachers in CPP Implementation in terms of Community Participation and Age Groupings

Area	Younger		Older	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
C. Community Participation <i>As a teacher, I am ...</i>				
1. keeping in touch with our community leaders to assist victims and help their families cope with violent	3.57	High Level	3.70	High Level

experiences.

2. providing support, financially or morally, to the children of our community who are victims of violence at home.	3.71	High Level	4.03	High Level
3. giving assistance to the parents of the victims by guiding them to seek counseling or professional help.	3.99	High Level	4.07	High Level
4. helping the community by training the parents on what to do when they or their children are subjected to violent situations.	3.53	High Level	3.59	High Level
5. assisting community leaders or social workers in making sure that victims are fully protected and the incident is properly reported to authorities.	4.12	High Level	4.12	High Level
Overall Mean	3.80	High Level	3.88	High Level

Table 12 shows the overall mean scores of 3.80 for the younger group and 3.88 for the older group, which is interpreted as a high level. Item no. 5 got the highest mean score of 4.12 for the younger group and 4.12 for the older group, interpreted as high level. Meanwhile, item no. 4 got the lowest mean score of 3.53 for the younger and 3.59 for the older group, interpreted as high level. The results reveal that some teachers are not cooperative enough to get engaged in community efforts to educate parents about child protection and perhaps early detection techniques of child abuse. This can be attributed to the fact that teachers also have higher loads. Every type of abuse carries the risk of having a lasting effect on the victim and impairing their capacity to operate as human beings. Abuse leaves victims feeling worthless, despondent, and unable to lead full lives. It also undermines their sense of self-worth and self-esteem. Long-term effects of child abuse include low educational attainment, problems finishing tasks, an inability to live life as planned, an inability to take care of oneself, an inability to lead a family, a persistent health issue, a lack of confidence, and a propensity for addiction, low self-esteem, depression, and anxiety, post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD), attachment difficulties, eating disorders, poor peer relationships, and self-injurious behavior (such as attempts at suicide) (Melton, 2019).

Table 13

Level of Compliance of Teachers in CPP Implementation in terms of Service Delivery and Length of Service

Area	Shorter		Longer	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
B. Service Delivery <i>As a teacher, I am ...</i>				
1. educating learners to approach me or any teacher to report any instance of bullying in school or any form of abuse they encounter.	3.84	High Level	3.77	High Level
2. working closely with our team in gathering information if there are reported cases of violence against children.	4.08	High Level	4.01	High Level
3. providing suggestions on how to provide quicker solutions to complaints.	3.98	High Level	3.84	High Level
4. helping in the identification and protection of the victim.	3.83	High Level	3.68	High Level
5. cooperating with the initiatives of the school in providing faster resolution to reported cases.	3.52	High Level	3.58	High Level
Overall Mean	3.85	High Level	3.78	High Level

Table 13 shows the overall mean scores of 3.85 for the shorter group and 3.78 for the longer group, which is interpreted as a high level. Item no. 2 got the highest mean score of 4.08 for the shorter group and 4.01 for the longer group, interpreted as a high level. Meanwhile, item no. 5 got the lowest mean score of 3.52 for the shorter group and 3.58 for the longer group, which can be interpreted as a high level. The main programmatic response from both government and non-government organizations for victims of child abuse, neglect, and abandonment is residential care, which is institutional care given in a setting other than a family. According to the DSWD's most recent data (2016), 915 private social welfare organizations have licenses from the agency; 177 of those organizations run 197 residential care facilities for children and adolescents. For children who have been the victims of abuse, are homeless, or suffer from mental illness, 46 residential care facilities are directly run by the Department of Social Welfare and Development (DSWD, 2016).

Table 14

Level of Compliance of Teachers in CPP Implementation in terms of Community Participation and Length of Service

Area	Shorter		Longer	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
C. Community Participation				

As a teacher, I am ...

1. keeping in touch with our community leaders to assist victims and help their families cope with violent experiences.	3.58	High Level	3.68	High Level
2. providing support, financially or morally, to the children of our community who are victims of violence at home.	3.77	High Level	3.94	High Level
3. giving assistance to the parents of the victims by guiding them to seek counseling or professional help.	4.03	High Level	4.01	High Level
4. helping the community by training the parents on what to do when they or their children are subjected to violent situations.	3.56	High Level	3.52	High Level
5. assisting community leaders or social workers in making sure that victims are fully protected and the incident is properly reported to authorities.	4.11	High Level	4.14	High Level
Overall Mean	3.82	High Level	3.86	High Level

Table 14 shows the overall mean scores of 3.82 for the shorter group and 3.86 for the longer group, which is interpreted as high level. Item no. 5 got the highest mean score of 4.11 for the shorter group and 4.14 for the longer group, interpreted as high level. Meanwhile, item no. 4 got the lowest mean score of 3.56 for the shorter and 3.54 for the longer group, interpreted as high level. Child neglect is more common in developing nations like the Philippines because families there are more likely to experience poverty and its related problems. However, neglect is a controversial idea in the context of emerging nations. For instance, in high-income nations, it would be considered neglect to deny children access to food, clean water, healthcare, and education, yet in extreme poverty, these necessities are extremely impossible to provide (Ramiro et al., 2016).

Table 15

Level of Compliance of Teachers in CPP Implementation in terms of Service Delivery and Family Income

Area	Lower		Higher	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
B. Service Delivery				
<i>As a teacher, I am ...</i>				
1. educating learners to approach me or any teacher to report any instance of bullying in school or any form of abuse they encounter.	3.78	High Level	3.85	High Level
2. working closely with our team in gathering information if there are reported cases of violence against children.	4.00	High Level	4.11	High Level
3. providing suggestions on how to provide quicker solutions to complaints.	3.90	High Level	3.94	High Level
4. helping in the identification and protection of the victim.	3.67	High Level	3.89	High Level
5. cooperating with the initiatives of the school in providing faster resolution to reported cases.	3.57	High Level	3.52	High Level
Overall Mean	3.78	High Level	3.86	High Level

Table 15 shows the overall mean scores of 3.78 for the lower group and 3.86 for the higher group, which is interpreted as a high level. Item no. 2 got the highest mean score of 4.00 for the lower group and 4.11 for the higher group, interpreted as a high level. Meanwhile, item no. 5 got the lowest mean score of 3.57 for the lower group and 3.52 for the higher group, interpreted as a high level. It is said that any media plan aimed at raising the standard of reporting on human rights and society must include professional and sensitive journalism as a fundamental component. Covering children and their rights presents a particular everyday challenge for journalists and media organizations. These guidelines are intended to serve as a helpful resource for journalists and government agencies covering child abuse situations. More specifically, media coverage is crucial in drawing attention to problems and worries about child protection. But this should always be done considering the children and their families, acting tactfully (Dooley, 2021).

Table 16

Level of Compliance of Teachers in CPP Implementation in terms of Community Participation and Family Income

Area	Lower		Higher	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
C. Community Participation				
<i>As a teacher, I am ...</i>				
1. keeping in touch with our community leaders to assist victims and help their families cope with violent experiences.	3.54	High Level	3.75	High Level

2. providing support, financially or morally, to the children of our community who are victims of violence at home.	3.68	High Level	4.00	High Level
3. giving assistance to the parents of the victims by guiding them to seek counseling or professional help.	4.01	High Level	4.04	High Level
4. helping the community by training the parents on what to do when they or their children are subjected to violent situations.	3.57	High Level	3.58	High Level
5. assisting community leaders or social workers in making sure that victims are fully protected and the incident is properly reported to authorities.	4.16	High Level	4.09	High Level
Overall Mean	3.79	High Level	3.90	High Level

Table 16 shows the overall mean scores of 3.79 for the lower group and 3.90 for the higher group, which is interpreted as a high level. Item no. 5 got the highest mean score of 4.16 for the lower group and 4.09 for the higher group, interpreted as high level. Meanwhile, item no. 1 got the lowest mean score of 3.54 for the lower group, and item no. 4 also got the lowest mean score of 3.58 for the higher group, interpreted as high level. This implies that some teachers are non-cooperative or less engaged with the community in its effort to resolve the problem of child abuse. By passing on the opportunity to take part in this noble cause, teachers may have other good reasons for doing so. However, one should always respond tactfully and with care for the children and their families (Dooley, 2021).

Table 17
Difference in the Extent of Teachers' Compliance in CPP Implementation in Service Delivery when Grouped according to the Aforementioned Demographics

Variable	Category	N	Mean Rank	Mann Whitney U	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
Age	Younger	97	90.53	3053.000	0.117		Not Significant
	Older	73	78.82				
Length of Service	Shorter	93	88.05	3343.000	0.447	0.05	Not Significant
	Longer	77	82.42				
Family income	Lower	99	92.44	2827.500	0.027		Significant
	Higher	71	75.82				

Table 17 shows that there is no significant difference in the Extent of Compliance of Teachers in the Implementation of Child Protection Policy (CPP) in the Area Service Delivery when grouped and compared according to age and length of service while in the variable family income shows significant difference which means that the lower-income respondents have a different opinion from that of the higher-income respondents. This means that their differing opinions on service delivery critically affect how they carry out their roles in implementing the program. In this case, the low-income group was more satisfied with service delivery, while the higher-income group believes otherwise and wants to accomplish more. Child Protection is a broad term that describes philosophies, policies, standards, guidelines, and procedures to protect children from intentional and unintentional harm. In this document the term "child protection" applies to protection of children in international schools (AISA, 20164).

Table 18
Difference in the Extent of Teachers' Compliance in CPP Implementation in Community Involvement when Grouped according to the Aforementioned Demographics

Variable	Category	N	Mean Rank	Mann Whitney U	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
Age	Younger	97	78.76	2886.500	0.037		Significant
	Older	73	94.46				
Length of Service	Shorter	93	81.21	3181.500	0.206	0.05	Not Significant
	Longer	77	90.68				
Family income	Lower	99	83.24	3291.000	0.475		Not Significant
	Higher	71	88.65				

Table 18 shows that there is a significant difference in the Extent of Compliance of Teachers in the Implementation of Child Protection Policy (CPP) in the community participation when grouped and compared according to age in terms of community participation while there is no significant difference in terms of length of service and family income. This means that the younger respondents' opinion differs from the older respondents and their opinion will serve as an impediment to the implementation of some programs. The school may need to patch up these differences to move forward with a successful program. Schools shall be conducive to children's education, and that the children's best interest shall be the primary consideration in all policies and actions of educational institutions. The study recommends that the teachers be capacitated through continuing professional development programs to provide special protection to children who are seriously susceptible or threatened by situations that distress their normal growth and may also be conducted to further policy's improved implementation in the public schools in the Philippine context (Dela Fuente, 2021).

Table 19
Difference in the Extent of Teachers' Compliance in CPP Implementation in Service Delivery when Grouped according to the Aforementioned Demographics

Variable	Category	N	Mean Rank	Mann Whitney U	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
Age	Younger	97	86.52	3441.500	0.753		Not Significant
	Older	73	84.14				
Length of Service	Shorter	93	88.96	3258.500	0.308	0.05	Not Significant
	Longer	77	81.32				
Family income	Lower	99	81.71	3139.500	0.231		Not Significant
	Higher	71	90.78				

Table 19 shows that there is no significant difference in the Level of Compliance of Teachers in the Implementation of Child Protection Policy (CPP) in the Area of Service Delivery when grouped and compared according to the aforementioned variables. This means that age, length of service, and family income do not affect the respondents' opinions when assessing the service delivery of the CPP. Furthermore, this means that all respondents have the same level of commitment to making sure that service delivery in terms of CPP is really high. The study of Casipe (2023) aimed to explore teachers' sentiments in implementing child protection policies. The findings of the thematic analysis of the interview transcription revealed that teachers lack a deep understanding of the policy; there is a tendency for students to abuse the policy, and teachers demand policy amendments. In addressing such sentiments, it was noted that teachers should observe proper monitoring and coordination, embrace effective strategies to address possible student abuse of the policy and address teachers' collective sentiments. It was then learned that teachers' insights in implementing child protection policy include being accountable when difficult situations occur, realizing the importance of sharing good values with students, establishing positive relationships with students and parents and leading a child-centered and policy-based institution.

Table 20
Difference in the Extent of Teachers' Compliance in CPP Implementation in Community Participation when Grouped according to the Aforementioned Demographics

Variable	Category	N	Mean Rank	Mann Whitney U	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
Age	Younger	97	80.62	3067.500	0.129		Not Significant
	Older	73	91.98				
Length of Service	Shorter	93	83.46	3391.000	0.545	0.05	Not Significant
	Longer	77	87.96				
Family income	Lower	99	80.32	3001.500	0.099		Not Significant
	Higher	71	92.73				

Table 20 shows that there is no significant difference in the Level of Commitment of Teachers in the Implementation of Child Protection Policy (CPP) in the Area Community Participation when grouped and compared according to the aforementioned variables. This means that all respondents have the same shared level of commitment in terms of community participation. This means that a huge majority of the respondents are truly committed to upholding the mandate of the Child Protection Policy, which is guaranteed by the Constitution. Bayucca (2020) determined the teachers' level of awareness of the Child Protection Policy and the level of its implementation in the Schools Division of Meycauayan City. The study found that most teachers are aware of the Child Protection Policy, but its implementation in the schools is flexible. Therefore, it is recommended that the implementation of the Child Protection Policy be monitored and that a more comprehensive information drive be given to teachers. Training modules that include positive and non-violent discipline in classroom management, anger and stress management, and gender sensitivity should be included in seminars to be conducted.

Table 21
Relationship Between Teachers' Extent of Compliance and Level of Commitment in CPP Implementation

Variable	rho	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
Extent of Compliance				
	1.000	0.031	0.05	Significant
Level of Commitment				

Table 21 shows that there is a significant relationship between the extent of compliance and level of commitment of teachers in the implementation of CPP. The results show that teachers' compliance with the program increases their commitment. This also establishes that the more engaged the teachers are in the CPP implementation, the more committed they tend to be. That means longer exposure or participation in the program leads to a better commitment. Strong commitments and compliance from all of the major players in society who have different responsibilities and roles pertaining to the protection of children are necessary for a systems-based approach to child protection. In this sense, the educational system is essential. Child protection must be integrated into school policies and procedures, curricula, hiring, and staff development. Education systems oriented on child safety may undergo significant adjustments in how they operate, how students interact with them and behave in the classroom, and how teachers interact with students and their families (Mohan, 2018).

Conclusions

Based on the analyzed and interpreted data presented in this study, teachers' high levels of compliance guarantee minimal child protection issues while a high level of commitment is a positive indicator, regular assessments, ongoing training, and continuous improvement efforts are essential to ensure sustained effectiveness in child protection measures. When grouped and compared according to the aforementioned variables, all areas in terms of compliance and in commitment were all on a high level. This means that regardless of their circumstances, the teachers are highly committed to implementing CPP in schools and understand the need to implement this program and they cooperate with authorities to ensure that students are fully protected in school. There was no significant difference in the extent of compliance and level of commitment of teachers in the implementation of CPP. This means that the respondents' opinions are within the same range regardless of their classification and circumstances. This is good for school implementation because everyone agrees with the implementation in principle; thus, there is no resistance. And this is also a good sign that CPP implementation in schools will have stronger support from the teachers. Teachers are parents, too; they are considered secondary parents while students are in school. Lastly, there was significant relationship between the extent of compliance and the level of commitment of teachers in implementing CPP shows that the higher the extent of compliance, the more teachers gets committed to the program. Based on the results obtained in this study, the following actions are recommended to be undertaken: 1) review existing policies and procedures in the implementation of child protection policies; 2) re-train and continue to raise awareness among teachers on the importance of CPP implementation; and 3) engage the parents in CPP since not all abuses happen in school, but sometimes, if not often, they happen at home.

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